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Art Installation as a Research Tool in Interdisciplinary School Projects

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Abstract: Our study explores the integration of installation art within interdisciplinary educational projects, focusing on its potential to engage students in addressing complex social, environmental, and historical problems. By examining various projects, such as exhibitions highlighting environmental pollution or historical events like the Holocaust, our research

demonstrates that creating installation art allows students to explore and understand complex topics in a creative way. The findings indicate that involving students in the creation of installations fosters critical thinking, enhances their artistic skills, and promotes public discourse. The study emphasizes the importance of collaboration among educators across disciplines and underscores the transformative power of art in education, illustrating how it can serve as a catalyst for social awareness and community engagement, preparing students to confront and analyze pressing societal challenges in an informed and creative manner.

Keywords: installation, art, interdisciplinary approach, research, educational projects, social issues, science, history.

Rezumat: Articolul explorează integrarea artei instalației în proiectele educaționale interdisciplinare, punând accentul pe potențialul său de a implica elevii în abordarea problemelor sociale, de mediu și istorice complexe. Prin examinarea diverselor proiecte, cum ar fi expozițiile ce evidențiază poluarea mediului sau evenimentele istorice precum Holocaustul, cercetarea demonstrează că realizarea artei instalației le permite elevilor să exploreze și să înțeleagă subiecte complexe într-un mod creativ. Rezultatele indică faptul că implicarea elevilor în crearea instalațiilor le stimulează gândirea critică, le îmbunătățește abilitățile artistice și promovează discursul public. Studiul subliniază importanța colaborării între pedagogii de diverse discipline și evidențiază puterea transformatoare a artei în educație, ilustrând modul în care aceasta poate acționa ca un catalizator pentru conștientizarea socială și implicarea comunității, pregătind elevii să se confrunte cu și să analizeze provocările sociale presante într-un mod informat și creativ.

Cuvinte-cheie: instalație, artă, abordare interdisciplinară, cercetare, proiecte educaționale, probleme sociale, știință, istorie.

School disciplines are often represented in interdisciplinary research projects. Educators across various fields have extensive opportunities for creative approaches and can engage students through innovative ideas. However, a question arises: what would happen if we attempted to unite some disciplines under the common concept of „art”, allowing students to investigate a problem from a new perspective? This presents an intriguing challenge for educators and an opportunity for collaboration among colleagues. There are various concepts in which art, particularly in the form of installations, can be integrated. These may include individual disciplines working together within the framework of interdisciplinary projects (History, Literature), as well as concepts such as STEM.

Teachers actively integrate this concept into their work with students, sharing their experiences by conducting workshops and training sessions for colleagues. Developing skills within the concept of STEM disciplines prepares students to tackle questions and challenges in their professional fields [2]. This leads to the conclusion that it would be highly beneficial for students to engage in project-based work starting from their school years. The future evolution

of the pedagogical concept defining STEM education is closely tied to the open nature of the reality it reflects, which emphasizes a global, integrative approach to all forms of knowledge and human intelligence essential for the information society of both the present and the future. In this context, another model, known as STEAM education, where we add an A for Art, is gaining popularity in schools. We believe that art has the potential to extend beyond this concept while serving as its cornerstone [1; 2].

Art is almost always used in these projects, taking various forms such as posters, lap books, practical three-dimensional works, animations, drawings, and more. All of these methods help students visualize the problem and study it better, allowing them to absorb more information through practical and creative components than they would through a traditional disciplinary approach [3].

We mentioned art as a key element in implementing and enhancing school projects, specifically focusing on installation art as the final product of such activities. The term originates from the verb „to install”, which inherently implies assembling the work from several individual parts [5]. Installations often occupy large spaces – entire halls, a series of rooms in a museum, outdoor venues etc. Artists communicate with the audience through their creations, highlighting important themes that concern them and drawing society’s attention to various problems. Installations typically emerge in an artist’s practice at moments when traditional forms, such as painting, can no longer convey the complexity of a situation. It is essential to teach the new generation of students effective communication with society, demonstrating ways and opportunities for them to express their concerns to the world and to show how they may be heard [4].

Creating installations as part of a school project offers several educational and developmental benefits:

Enhances creativity: Installation projects encourage students to think outside the box and explore innovative solutions, fostering creativity and artistic expression.

Promotes collaboration: Working on an installation often involves teamwork, helping students develop communication and collaboration skills as they share ideas and responsibilities.

Promoting interdisciplinary approaches: Installations can integrate multiple academic disciplines, such as art, science, history, and social studies, by creating a comprehensive educational experience. This interdisciplinary framework reflects the principles of integrative learning, which emphasizes the connections between various fields of knowledge.

Enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills: The complexity of planning and executing installations requires the students to engage in critical analysis and problem-solving.

Increasing cultural and social awareness: Through artistic installations, students can stand up and tell us

about various social issues, fostering empathy and an understanding of diverse cultural perspectives. This aligns with the transformative learning theory, which posits that critical reflection on societal issues can lead to personal and social change.

Active engagement: Creating installations involves hands-on learning, which can be more engaging than traditional classroom methods. This active participation can enhance retention and understanding of the subject matter.

Reflective practice: Students learn to reflect on their work and its impact, developing a deeper understanding of the creative process and the importance of feedback in improving their skills.

Personal expression: Installation projects provide a platform for personal expression, allowing the students to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and ideas in a unique and impactful way.

Environmental issues: science/biology and art. There is a significant potential for integrating art into interdisciplinary projects by combining it with fields such as biology, history, physics, and others. One potential approach is to use installations to raise awareness about environmental problems, particularly pollution. For example, a school campaign could focus around innovative methods for recycling plastic waste, encouraging a more sustainable and responsible use of natural resources.

One project we implemented was centered on creating installations as a practical application of an interdisciplinary educational approach aimed at exploring environmental pollution. It involved 30 classes from both elementary and middle school levels, with the project structure adjusted to suit the students’ respective educational stages. For younger students the project was framed as a school project, while for older students it became an interdisciplinary project, combining elements of ecology, art, and science. The main goals were to explore environmental problems and raise awareness about pollution and waste recycling. Through creative installations the students explored topics such as pollution and waste disposal, with their impact on ecosystems and human life. The process of creating the installations encouraged in-depth research and a more thorough understanding of these environmental challenges, resulting in a public exhibition.

Ocean Pollution. A significant part of the exhibition was a large-scale reproduction of Katsushika Hokusai’s *The Great Wave off Kanagawa* (3x2 meters), made using non-recyclable plastic waste. To create this artwork, students researched the types of waste that commonly pollute the oceans, how it reaches marine environments, and its impact on ecosystems. The installation incorporated three-dimensional elements such as plastic bottles, containers, and packaging, which were placed both on the surface of the „water” and spread around the installation area, representing the extent of marine pollution (Figure no. 1).

Figure no. 1. Figure no. 2. Figure no. 3. Figure no. 4.
Ocean Pollution Ocean Pollution Global Warming Marine Life

Impact of Ocean Pollution on Marine Life. This set of installations complemented the previous one, highlighting the effects of pollution on marine species. It included figures of birds, fish, and sea creatures (Figure no. 4) made from waste materials that harm these species. For example, a seagull was constructed from disposable plastic cutlery and bottle caps to represent how birds ingest plastic waste, mistaking it for food. Additionally, the students created fish and coral figures from plastic waste, and a turtle was made from plastic bags and fabric scraps. The turtle was designed to symbolize the common phenomenon where turtles mistake floating plastic bags for jellyfish. The turtle figure was wrapped in wire to symbolize how waste can entangle marine animals, restricting their movement and causing harm. These figures created a unified composition that conveyed the gravity of ocean pollution.

Global Warming and Melting Glaciers. Two installations addressed the problem of global warming and its impact on polar ecosystems. One showed a polar bear standing on a small melting iceberg, crafted from cardboard using geometric techniques. The second installation also was a polar bear, but this time holding the Earth in its paws, urging viewers to reflect on the global consequences of climate change, particularly the danger it poses to species such as polar bears (Figure no. 3).

Overconsumption and Overproduction. This installation focused on the problem of consumerism and the overproduction of goods, ranging from clothing and electronics to toys and accessories. As the centerpiece, we borrowed a large shopping cart from a supermarket and decorated it with thread, paper, and cardboard to make it visually attractive. Inside the cart, we placed items that often go unsold or are discarded shortly after being produced. The installation was intended to provoke reflection on how attractive consumer goods seem while questioning whether we truly need everything we purchase.

The exhibition was further enhanced by informational posters hung from the upper windows of the school. These posters, created by students, contained visual data and graphics related to the topics of pollution, overcon-

sumption, and ecology problems. They served to further educate visitors and reinforce the messages conveyed by the installations. In addition, art installations can be employed to raise awareness about the problem of stray animals and uncontrolled population growth. These projects could serve as an educational tool, informing the public about effective measures such as neutering and responsible pet care.

The exhibition, set up in the school courtyard, was open to the public and attracted a large audience, including parents, teachers, students, local media (Figure no. 8), and community members. This project demonstrated how interdisciplinary school initiatives can effectively foster understanding of critical environmental issues. It also showed how a school project can engage the wider public in thinking critically about their role in environmental sustainability.

We Remember the Holocaust: History and Art. In moving away from STEM projects, exploring history through art offers new opportunities to contemplate significant historical events. Art installations can also serve as an educational tool to enhance students' understanding of complex historical events, such as the Holocaust, emphasizing the importance of preserving historical memory. Through art, we can highlight the destructive nature of wars and genocide and underscore the need to prevent such tragedies in the future. Even the Auschwitz Museum has incorporated installations into its exhibitions. The exhibition includes glass displays showcasing personal belongings such as clothing, eyeglasses, prosthetics, chinaware, and even human hair. By presenting these artifacts, the installations evoke a powerful emotional response, allowing visitors to grasp the human impact of the Holocaust on a more personal level. The *We Remember the Holocaust* project aimed to provide an in-depth analysis of the catastrophic consequences of war and Nazi crimes while fostering a profound understanding of the tragedy of the Holocaust among students and society. The project focused on a research-oriented approach that combined historical analysis with artistic installations, letting students to engage more deeply with the material.

Figure no. 5. Figure no. 6. Figure no. 7. Figure no. 8.
Installation Installation. Details Installation. Details Local media

The project emphasized the importance of studying themes related to war and its catastrophic consequences for humanity. The interdisciplinary approach through art provided students with the opportunity to interpret historical events through an emotional and visual lens.

The installations created by students are complex artistic constructions that integrate historical data and symbolism. The use of materials such as clay, metal (Figure no. 7), and collages helped recreate the imagery of concentration and death camps, contributing to a cohesive composition. Key elements of the installations – trains, barbed wire, children’s shoes (Figure no. 6), facial expressions, colors, and textures – served as visual metaphors that encouraged deep reflection on the victims and their suffering. These artistic decisions acted as emotionally charged components, enhancing the viewer’s experience and conveying the tragedy on a symbolic level (Figure no. 5)

A fundamental aspect of the project included research trips for students to the memorial complexes of Auschwitz and Birkenau. This experience allowed participants to witness firsthand the consequences of the Holocaust and the historically significant sites they had studied at school. Experiencing the tragedy at its historical site heightened students’ motivation to further study and disseminate knowledge about the subject.

The project’s final phase culminated in an exhibition of installations that served as a display of the students’ research results and a platform for public discourse on the Holocaust. The students presented their collected data, integrating it with creative visual elements, thereby informing viewers and the invited media about the significance of historical memory. The exhibition attracted widespread public attention and allowed the students to demonstrate their ability to explore and interpret complex historical themes through art.

Institutions should offer workshops and training sessions for teachers to familiarize them with inter-

disciplinary teaching methods and the effective use of installation art as a pedagogical tool. This direction of professional development can enhance the teachers’ capabilities to guide students in creative projects. Schools should try to integrate installation art projects into the existing curriculum across various disciplines. This approach will encourage students to explore topics from multiple angles and enhance their critical thinking skills. Projects that involve the creation of installations facilitate experiential learning. This hands-on approach enhances students’ comprehension of the subject matter while cultivating essential skills such as teamwork and creativity. By adopting these recommendations, educational institutions can cultivate a more enriching learning environment that enhances students’ artistic skills.

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